

ARTISTIC EXPRESSION AND INTERPRETATION OF IMAGES IN THE STORIES OF NAZAR ESHANKUL.

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In his works, Nazar Eshanqul describes the human state of mind not with lively words, but depicts it through artistic means. Rebellion against nature, society, and humanity surrounding suffering is expressed through colors, smells, and pictures. In particular, “Art -1”, “Art – 2”, “Photograph of a ruined city”, “Black book”, “Coffin city”, and “Monkey leading by the man” showcase this style of the writer. In this way, the writer conveys meditative states to the reader through pictures rather than words, leaving the interpretation and feedback to the reader. Each character of the reader who writes through the picture and colors in the work leads to the spiritual world and social situations in society through symbolic artistic interpretation. In particular, in the writer's work “The Monkey Led by the Man,” the old man's pictures take the reader on a journey to the world of that time. These pictures depict individuals who are suffering incomparably, separated from everything, separated from themselves, and handing themselves to the world, showing the inner world of a person who is shaken. They resemble the works of great artists. In these pictures, those who have not overcome their memories are on the path of fate.

“The porch is long, and the paintings seem to be exhibited according to the years they were painted - typed, or rather only about forty photos and sketches from “1957”, “1947”, “1937”, “1928”, “1926”, and so on.

As I scrolled through the photos, I saw an old man's life talisman from some stairs. I felt as if I was climbing towards a hidden fortress...

In the work, as we read these lines, it is not difficult to understand that it refers to the reality of the past. Especially the pace of painting in “1921” attracts attention. “The picture is drawn in a rather clumsy way; however, the colors are bright and clear. In the photo, a burly young man is depicted leading a monkey through a dark forest on a rising bar. The young man's eyes are bright and confident. The monkey's handcuffs are tight, and the red and rye paint fully reflects the feelings of the young man”¹.

These images in the works of Nazar Eshanqul are people of that time.

1. ¹ Эшонқул Н. Момоқўшиқ: қисса ва ҳикоялар. – Тошкент: Ғафур Ғулом, 2019. – 332 б.

A typical representative of the image - a reflection of the mental state of an old man in colors serves to enter life with great confidence, the image of a young man full of views, capable of subjugating the world, is embodied. In his paintings, painted in later periods, the colors found their place, nature the landscape is becoming more and more beautiful, the colors are becoming more and more diverse, but the following abstractness of paintings, like autumn crows covering the sky in the images, disappears. Black colors begin to displace other colors. In the thirties, the black color completely occupies the painted pictures.

It happens that the first painted picture became a representation of a feeling called hope, depicting the appearance of disappointments in life and the faith of a young man through colors turning into an image.

In conclusion, we can say that the hero of the work, suffering from hallucinations, takes on a leading role. There is a high syncretism of interpretations of psychological and tragic situations in the image of such heroes. The works of Nazar Eshankul have been found, demonstrating this type of spirituality and symbols of a mentally defective soul. In the form of a coffin in the story "Coffin". The image of a person who is an architect of urban construction is such a hallucinatory disease, a person who is a thief. N. Eshankul has many attractive moments in this story. He wrote about the fate of the victims of the Shura era. N. Eshankul in his works, putting on the mask of good in the face of evil, in the name of man in the 20th century, especially in the later history of mankind, where evil acts in the name of good recreates the heroes of an era when it was difficult to distinguish good from evil. Because evil also uses the language and words used by good, which is also what kindness worries about. It was hard to tell from his face. In the works of N. Eshankul feels a rebellion of the soul, a spiritual impulse, a confused heart. The existential philosophy that "rebellion is the essence of man", originally from Baudelaire, marked the beginning of Baudelaire's poetry - a vivid example of creativity and rebellion. This madness in the East, also called N. Eshankul, also revolts against evil in his works. When the rebellion of the intellect fades, talent also fades, says the writer who was with H. Norboy in conversation. In particular, when a writer comments on Kafka's works, his work is the greatest Both Jarayon and Korgon declare that this is an uprising. We also Reading N. Eshonkul's works, images, colors, stench and ugly smells in them, rebellion in the human spirit, expression of social protest in the human heart through paintings, we will witness this.

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